

eco-union

**Blue
eco forum**

**Towards Sustainable
Blue Food in the Mediterranean**
CONFERENCE REPORT 2021 —

eco-union

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Eco-union is a citizen environmental Think and Do Tank dedicated to bridging the gap between science, policies and practices towards Sustainability of the Euro-Mediterranean region. It has been organizing the Blue Eco Forums, multi stakeholders and participatory annual events aiming to inspire and act towards environmental and social sustainability in the Mediterranean region. Since 2008 they have gathered opinion leaders and change agents to promote dialogue, innovation and collaboration from key actors of the Euro-Mediterranean region. The focus has been on the critical issues related to sustainable development, climate change, renewable energy, coastal tourism and blue economy.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report of the Blue Eco Forum (BEF) 2021, organized virtually on October 22nd 2021, summarizes the contributions made by the participants, coming from different sectors and countries, to advance 'Towards Sustainable Blue Food in the Mediterranean'. Supported by Barcelona City, World Capital of Sustainable Food 2021, and MIO-ESCDE through Mediterranean Action Day 2021 on Ocean Literacy, the BEF 2021 presented different initiatives on Sustainable Food and climate action in the Mediterranean contributing to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (the Ocean Decade). This report brings up knowledge about Policy, Management or Behavioral tools such as Marine Planning, ecological footprint or eco-labels to inform sound decision-making related to sustainable blue food. Besides, the present document provides key insights, policy recommendations and shared visions to strengthen the development of blue, low-carbon and resilient food systems in the Mediterranean region.

After a short introduction with main facts and figures on Blue Food, the first part presents different statements made by the participants, tackling a diversity of issues. During the discussions, particular attention was given to both the challenges and opportunities of Blue Food, putting emphasis on the idea that if challenges are actively and ambitiously managed, the Blue Food sector could provide many opportunities for human and environmental well-being. Innovative practices, such as introducing more circularity, using the principles of permaculture or relying on alternative foods, are crucial in this move towards more sustainability. The role of consumers has also been highlighted, analyzing their behaviour concerning seafood, and discussing the appropriate market tools to improve consumption patterns. Lastly, the BEF 2021 also has shown that there is room for improvement in terms of policy coherence, integrated policies, participatory governance, legal support and synergies in order to achieve a Circular Blue Economy in the Mediterranean.

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1 STATE OF BLUE FOOD IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

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1. STATE OF BLUE FOOD IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

Blue foods, also referred to as aquatic foods, include **animals, plants and microorganisms that are farmed in and harvested from water, as well as cell- and plant-based foods emerging from new technologies**¹. Aquatic foods can be farmed or wild-caught, and are sourced from inland, coastal and marine waters, producing a diversity of foods across all seasons and geographic regions². According to the latest figures from the 2020 edition of *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture*³ (FAO), **the global production of Blue food has reached 214 million tons in 2018**, and includes more than 2,500 species⁴. In the Mediterranean area (including Black Sea), 2,3 million tonnes of aquatic foods were produced in 2019⁴.

Evolution of the quantity of aquatic food produced in the Mediterranean and Black Sea area between 2000 and 2019

1.1. HARVESTED AQUATIC FOOD

According to the recently published FAO data⁴, 1,390,000 tonnes of aquatic foods were harvested in 2019 in the Mediterranean area. Italy and Turkey, the two main producing countries, are responsible for respectively 23.3% and 15.2% of the total production. In the Mediterranean area, the importance of small-scale fisheries can't be denied, as they employ 57% of the fishery workforce and account for 83% of the vessel fleet in the area⁵. In 2018, 75% of fish stocks were exploited outside biologically sustainable limits. However, this percentage follows a consistent declining trend (88% in 2014)⁵.

1.2. AQUACULTURE

According to the recently published FAO data⁴, 887,000 tonnes of aquatic foods were produced via aquaculture in 2019 in the Mediterranean area. The aquaculture sector is segmented according to several criteria: the species farmed (fish farming, seaweed, molluscs...), the production technique (pond, culture, cage culture...), or the water environment (freshwater, brackish water or salt water). The four biggest producing countries are Egypt, Turkey, Greece and Italy, which together account for 87% of the aquaculture production in the Mediterranean area⁴.

¹ WorldFish. 2030 Research and Innovation Strategy: Aquatic Foods for Healthy People and Planet (eds Lala-Pritchard, T. & Johnstone, G) (WorldFish, 2020). ² Golden, C.D., Koehn, J.Z., Shepon, A. et al. Aquatic foods to nourish nations. *Nature* (2021). ³ FAO. 2020. *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020*. In brief. Sustainability in action. Rome. ⁴ FAO Global Fish Trade Statistics. Global Production by Production Source 1950–2019. FishStatJ (FAO, 2021). ⁵ FAO. 2020. *The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries 2020*. General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean. Rome.

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2. BLUE ECONOMY AND BLUE FOOD

The Blue Eco Forum (BEF) 2021 was opened by **Jeremie Fosse**, president of [eco-union](#), with a presentation of eco-union and the [Blue Eco Forums](#). At the core of this year's event is the topic of **Blue Food**, which is the food derived from aquatic animals, plants or algae that are caught or cultivated in freshwater and marine environments. **Blue Food** can make a significant contribution to food security, public health and climate action. Thus, it has the potential to play a key role in achieving the **Agenda 2030** and its **Sustainable Development Goals** (SDGs) by supporting healthier, more sustainable and more equitable food systems. In the Mediterranean, **Blue food**, coming today mainly from fisheries and aquaculture, is already a major sector of the **blue economy** with a strong impact and dependency on the quality of marine ecosystems. Shifting the way blue food is produced, regulated and consumed is critical to promote low-carbon and resilient Mediterranean societies.

2.1. BLUE ECONOMY IN BARCELONA

Pau Solanilla, Commissioner at the [Barcelona City Hall](#), stressed three particular messages in his intervention, revolving around the interconnection between the city of Barcelona and the Blue Economy. First of all, he insisted on **Barcelona's commitment to the Mediterranean**, not only because the city welcomes headquarters of important institutions, such as the Union for the Mediterranean, but also because of its location, making it a city open to the sea. Then, he pointed out that the **Blue Economy** is becoming more and more important to Barcelona, now representing **4,3% of the city's GDP**. Lastly, Pau Solanilla recalled that, as the intensification of climate change is calling us to act more ambitiously, Barcelona is taking this challenge seriously and presented the city's guidelines on the Blue Economy⁶. Based on 8 pillars, these guidelines tackle a diversity of issues such as investment, employment, innovation, development, civic engagement, ecosystem conservation, local and international positioning and public-private governance.

⁶ The official document with a detail of these measures can be found [here](#).

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Eight action axis to boost the Blue Economy in Barcelona

Source: *Ajuntament de Barcelona*

2.2. BLUE FOOD IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

Following this, **Michael Scoullos**, Chairman of the MIO-ECSDE (Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development) stressed the importance of sustainable development, especially based on local products, and including products from the ocean. In the 80s, aquaculture was not as developed as it is nowadays and the enthusiasm around these new methods made stakeholders oblivious of the potential damages on ecosystems, of which we are now more aware. Lastly, Michael Scoullos insisted on the idea that what is discussed here has deep **cultural and social roots**, and represents a treasure that needs to be safeguarded and made productive for the current and future generations.

3 OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR A SUSTAINABLE BLUE FOOD ECOSYSTEM

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In this session, relevant stakeholders and international experts explored the challenges, opportunities, barriers and needs related to sustainable blue food ecosystems in the Mediterranean region, with a special focus on environmental impacts, governance issues, behavioral, management or market instruments.

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3.1. BLUE MANIFESTO

Tobias Troll, Marine Policy director at Seas At Risk and moderator of this session, started with a presentation of **Seas At Risk**, the European umbrella of NGOs defending the Ocean. The organization published the Blue Manifesto, a roadmap towards a healthy ocean by 2030 supported by around 100 organisations. Regarding Blue Food, the Manifesto promotes a just transition to **low impact fisheries**, as overfishing is responsible for biodiversity loss and jeopardizes the delicate balance of ecosystems. In the Mediterranean area, 93% of fish stocks are overfished. **Aquaculture** can be an alternative to wild caught fish, but runs the risk of reproducing the same mistakes as industrial livestock farming on land, including massive use of pharmaceuticals and pollution.

The documentary *Seaspiracy*⁷ brought the attention of the broader public on the existing threats and pressures on the ocean, including overfishing and aquaculture. Lastly, Tobias Troll stressed the contrast between the narrative around the idea of blue growth, and the fact that this productivist and extractivists model and thinking is precisely what created the challenges the Blue Food sector now has to face, both in terms of environmental (climate change, biodiversity loss etc.) and socio-economic challenges. He raised the question of the way in which we could shift to an **economy of sufficiency**, such as the **“doughnut economy”**⁸, taking into account both the planetary boundaries, or ecological ceiling, and the social boundaries, or what is considered essential in human lives.

3.2. BLUE FOOD ASSESSMENT INITIATIVE

Malin Jonell, researcher at the Stockholm Resilience Centre, specialist of the role of certification and market based instruments, and active member of the Blue Food Assessment (BFA) initiative, presented the **Blue Food Assessment initiative**. Led by the Stockholm Resilience Center, Stanford University and EAT and launched in September of this year⁹, it focuses on the role of Blue Food in current and future food systems on a global scale. Malin Jonell explained that Blue food includes fish, shellfish, aquatic plants, and algae that are captured or cultivated in the ocean, rivers, lakes, ponds and tanks. The challenges around Blue Food, a broad category designating more than 2,500 different species, has to be addressed because many people depend on them for their livelihood and nutrition, and demand in that sector is expected to double by 2050.

The first paper¹⁰, out of the five to be produced by the BFA initiative, on Blue Food and Nutrition, assembled for the first time the most comprehensive database on the **nutritional value of Blue foods**. One of its most important findings is that most Blue foods are richer in nutrients than many other terrestrial foods. A second paper¹¹, on the **environmental performance of Blue foods**, harmonized a variety of different environmental stressors, ranging from GHG emissions to land and water use. The results show that the environmental performance of Blue Food production is very variable, which is especially the case for land use, leaving much room for improvement. It turns out that many Blue Food species perform similar or better than chicken, with wild caught small pelagic fish and farmed bivalves producing the least GHG. Following this research, the BFA initiative issued five main recommendations for sustainable BF systems.

⁷ Seaspiracy. Ali Tabrizi. March 2021, Netflix. ⁸ About Doughnut Economics | DEAL. ⁹ The first report of the Blue Food Assessment can be found here. ¹⁰ Golden, C.D., Koehn, J.Z., Shepon, A. et al. Aquatic foods to nourish nations. *Nature* 598, 315–320 (2021). ¹¹ Gephardt, J.A., Henriksson, P.J.G., Parker, R.W.R. et al. Environmental performance of blue foods. *Nature* 597, 360–365 (2021).

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In the end, if the challenges associated with them are tackled effectively, Blue food can transform food systems to be healthy, diversified, equitable and sustainable. Food systems, be they green or blue, have to be thought of as a whole in order to maximize opportunities and minimize tradeoffs.

Five main recommendations of the Blue Food Assessment for sustainable Blue Food systems

3.3. MEDITERRANEAN STRATEGY FOR SUSTAINABLE FISHERIES AND AQUACULTURE

Housam Hamza, the GFCM (General Fisheries Commission of the Mediterranean) Aquaculture Officer started with an introduction to the regional organisation for the management of fisheries. On the 9th of July of this year, the 24 member countries adopted the 2030 GFCM strategy aimed at fostering a more responsible, sustainable and productive fisheries and aquaculture in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea. The sector of aquaculture, developing

very rapidly, is at the forefront of this blue transformation. Its importance and role in terms of food safety, employment and development can be understood through simple figures: this year, 3 million tonnes of Blue food have been produced by 35,000 different enterprises and employing, directly or indirectly, half a million people, making Blue Food production a key sector.

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Housam Hamza then entered in more detail on the 2030 GFCM strategy. The first pillar, out of the four dedicated to aquaculture, aims at fostering an **efficient governance** in support of responsible investment. The second pillar stresses the importance of promoting **sustainable practices** in the aquaculture industry and minimizing the environmental impact of the sector, which can be achieved for example using Allocated Zones for Aquaculture (AZA), as it has been done in Albania and Tunisia. Thirdly, the 2030 strategy focuses on improving the perception of aquaculture, including its **social acceptability**, by promoting good practices. Lastly, the fourth pillar consists of maximizing

the use of **technology and information systems** in order to make accessible to all the different actors the necessary technological tools and data. One example of how this strategy can be implemented concretely is the development, by the GFCM, of Aquaculture Demonstration Centers, with the objective of training researchers and administrators to adopt sustainable practices. To finish, Housam Hamza shared his vision of the Mediterranean region as a mosaic of good practices and lessons learned by different actors, the role of the GFCM being to bring them together.

Four expected outputs to achieve the sustainable development of the aquaculture sector

3.4. SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS PLATFORM IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

Sandro Dernini, Head of the Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean (SFS--MED) Platform Coordination Desk and General Secretary of the International Foundation of Mediterranean Diet (IFMeD), presented the **SFS-MED Platform**, an affiliated project of the UN One Planet Network Sustainable Food Systems Programme supported by the FAO,

CIHEAM and the Union for the Mediterranean Secretariat. This initiative was launched to promote sustainable food systems and provide food security in the region, in the footsteps of the Second World Conference on the revitalisation of the Mediterranean Diet organized in 2019. The **Mediterranean Diet** could be used as a lever to bridge sustainable consumption and sustainable production in order to cope with the multiple challenges this region is facing.

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Sandro Dernini insisted on the necessity to have a sustainable approach to food systems that is also **transdisciplinary**, to address the multiple and interdependent challenges. The Mediterranean region is an excellent opportunity to assess and understand the interconnections and synergies. The objective is to foster the dialogue not only between the different

stakeholders, but also between the different shores of the Mediterranean, which are otherwise fragmented. Sandro Dernini finished by recalling that it is impossible to talk about food systems in the Mediterranean without bringing in Blue Food on the table.

3.5. SUSTAINABILITY VS SUFFICIENCY

Tobias Troll (SAR) noted that the word sustainability was used intensively by all speakers, as it is the case ever since the Rio Earth Summit in 1992. However, despite this objective of sustainability, the world has developed in a very unsustainable way, as demonstrated by the following graphs.

Source : WWF Living Planet Report 2018

They show that **social and Earth indicators** (such as climate change, human growth, forest loss, ocean acidification, tourism...) are all pointing up in an exponential course in front of our eyes. He suggested that the concept of sustainability has probably become obsolete, and that it may be time to rather aim for sufficiency so as to not pretend sustainable growth is possible.

In reaction to this, **Malin Jonell** (BFA) pointed out that the [EAT Lancet Commission Report](#) on healthy diets from Sustainable Food Systems investigated whether or not we can produce

enough healthy food by 2050 for 10 billion people, and still keep within Earth boundaries. The outcome was positive: it is possible, but only if we radically transform how we produce food, and what food we consume. Amongst necessary steps to take, reducing red meat consumption and eating more plant-based food could be particularly impactful. In that sense, Blue Food has a crucial role to play. However, the fact that not all Blue foods are sustainable has to make us reflect on what we need and can afford in terms of food production and consumption.

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According to Sandro Dernini (SFS-Med), while the Blue Economy and Blue Food open many perspectives and opportunities, it has to be remembered, at every step of the process, that not all activities are sustainable. In addition, **Housam Hamza** pointed out the fact that the **Covid-19** crisis has enabled actors to realise the existing failures in the food system. The recommendations and resolutions adopted by the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) have the objective of coming to a consensus between member countries and finding ways to reach those goals. For example, the GFCM is encouraging its 24 member countries to turn to **polyculture and algae production**.

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The following session gathered the insights of three actors of the Mediterranean Blue Food ecosystem. Firstly, **Patricia Ricard**, President of the **Paul Ricard Oceanographic Institute**, a private research institute applying Circular Economy principles and working on Nature-based solutions to aquaculture systems. Secondly, Yago Sierras from Mediterranean Algae, a Spanish startup based in Alicante dedicated to the sustainable cultivation of algae native to the Mediterranean Sea. Thirdly, **Marika Azoff** from The **Good Food Institute**, a global nonprofit organization promoting a sustainable, secure, and just food system with alternative proteins like plant-based and cultivated seafood.

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4.1. CIRCULAR AQUACULTURE

Patricia Ricard, President of the Paul Ricard Oceanographic Institute, started with a presentation of the organization. The institute, created in 1966, has been participating in scientific research since the 70s with three successive scientific teams. They have developed knowledge on the impacts of human communities on the near shore, a critical area for ecosystems. All researchers at the Institute are divers, and work both in the field and in the laboratory to carry out their research. They have been working on a variety of different projects, including ecological restoration projects, and projects on the restoration of biocenosis at the European level. The evolution of the physico-chemical parameters of the ocean encourages actors to find alternatives and to protect both the climate and biodiversity. The Institute has accelerated its efforts on a production system called **Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture**, which corresponds to an onshore aquaculture farm based on the principles of permaculture¹².

It is urgent to change the way fish products are farmed, because aquaculture today is headed in the wrong direction. There are several reasons for this, including the usage of antibiotics and the fact that fish coming from aquaculture is fed using harvested fish, which increases pressure on already endangered fish stocks.

“Permaquaculture” intends to develop a system consisting of a whole trophic chain in communicating ponds, where only predatory fish are fed. The objective is to strictly control the physico-chemical parameters and to keep as many nutrients in the water as possible. The Institute has also developed a feed made out of insects to replace fish meal. Lastly, this type of aquaculture production system is based on a Circular Economy approach, with small farms connected to their local consumers and providing jobs for the community.

In reaction to this, Jeremie Fosse expressed interrogations on the possibility to develop this research on circular economy approaches in the aquaculture industry and into bigger markets, as well as on the extent to which regulatory frameworks could constitute barriers to their work. Patricia Ricard answered that these projects are made in a **scale down** approach, because scale up implies concentration of activities, making sustainability more difficult to attain. On the question of regulatory barriers, Patricia Ricard confirmed that the law can sometimes hold back some experimentation projects. For example, one of the Institute’s projects was aimed at developing shrimp farms in harbours to feed shrimps directly with fishing waste. However, the regulation forbids the use of waste from fisheries as food for fish farming.

¹² Permaculture is a production method based on “the conscious design and maintenance of agriculturally productive systems which have the diversity, stability, and resilience of natural ecosystems. It is the harmonious integration of the landscape with people providing their food, energy, shelter and other material and non-material needs in a sustainable way.”, Bill Mollison.

Description of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture system.

Source: Slide presented by Patricia Ricard

4.2. SUSTAINABLE SEAWEED

Yago Sierras, co-founder of the Spanish start-up created in 2020 and based in Alicante called Mediterranean Algae, presented their innovative initiative. With its transdisciplinary young team, the company works in the **seaweed sector** and aims to sell the seaweed products to the cosmetic, fertilizer and food industries.

The seaweed industry has a strong market position in the Asia-Pacific region, while, for the moment, the seaweed market remains small in Europe. The reason behind this is the difficult standardisation of seaweed products, as they are farmed in open-waters (i.e., polluted waters). This in turn poses risk to the consumers as they may ingest the particles that the seaweed has previously absorbed.

Mediterranean algae's work is focused on

converting this difficulty into an opportunity for the European seaweed market. They are standardising their products by applying technology in the **land-based cultivation system**, which cuts out the problem of pollution in the seaweed, or, in other words, avoids the derived health problems for open-water cultivated seaweed consumers. Moreover, farming seaweed in those closed systems is more efficient, with a higher yield/hectare than in open waters. Indeed, the laboratory enables greater control on both the chemical and the physical conditions, improving seaweed's growth, as more nutrients and more solar radiation lead to a higher production.

The start-up has four main ambitions at the moment. Firstly, it aims to illustrate how the seaweed industry has the potential to receive

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climate funding as a result of having captured CO₂ from the atmosphere. Secondly, it aspires to position the Mediterranean lettuce - endemic green seaweed from the Mediterranean (*Ulva lactuca*) as a Mediterranean diet supplement.

Given its high nutritional properties (vitamins A and C, iron, low-fat content, 50% fiber and 15% proteins), it could become a green alternative to the current protein market. Thirdly, it is exploring the **bioremediation potential** of their in-land cultivation system. Seaweeds act as biofilters as they absorb the pollutants such as nitrates and phosphates and turn them into organic matter. Therefore, on top of cleaning water systems (such as Mar Menor) they may be utilised to produce biofertilizers. Thereby, closing pollutant's cycle and accomplishing the European directives. Finally, the Spanish start-up is initiating a project in the old salt mines located in the Natural Park 'Salines de Santa Pola'. Their goal is to install a multi-trophic aquaculture system, as this type of aquaculture produces added value products in a sustainable way.

4.3. ALTERNATIVE SEAFOOD

Marika Azoff, corporate engagement specialist on sustainable seafood at the [Good Food Institute](#) (GFI), started by stressing the importance of bringing alternative seafood into this conversation on sustainable Blue Food

systems. The Good Food Institute is a non-profit organization funded by donors dedicated to accelerating the shift towards a healthy, sustainable and safe food supply for all.

The key question to address is the way in which we are going to **feed 10 billion people by 2050**. Some of GFI's solutions, explored in their [Sustainable Seafood Initiative](#), include making seafood products that people are used to buying in a more sustainable way and accelerating alternative proteins. In essence, the aim is to create **alternative seafood** with different textures and diversity of components, such as plants, microorganisms and shelves, without claiming to change consumer's minds, but changing companies in a way that they diversify food sources to increase the resilience of fish products. Alternative seafood encompasses all types of seafood made using fermentation, as well as plant-based and cultivated seafood. Today, **87 companies** are developing alternative seafood in the World. One example of the rapid development of these initiatives is the French company [Algama](#), which just received, in October, a 2M€ subsidy from the European Union to develop its activities. The advantages of alternative seafood are linked with many different SDGs, and not only n°14 "Life below water".

Description of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture system.

Source: Extract from the slides presented by Marika Azoff (GFI)

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The third session consisted of two interactive discussions, respectively on the topics of “Consumers, Markets and Lifestyle” and “Governance and Policies”. During both sessions, an interactive whiteboard was used¹³ to visually share the content exposed by the speakers.

¹³ The link to access the whiteboard can be found [here](#).

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5.1. CONSUMERS, MARKETS AND LIFESTYLE

The first interactive discussion, on the role of consumers, markets and lifestyle in this transition towards sustainable Blue Food systems, was moderated by **Laia Segura**, Policy Officer at **eco-union**. She introduced the interactive session linking this topic with what had already been explored by **Marika Azoff (GFI)**, stressing the role of seafood commercialisation, and **Sandro Dernini (SFS-Med)** who showed how the Mediterranean diet could be a ladder to achieve a more sustainable consumption of Blue food. The main question that was tackled is: **“How could consumer behaviours participate in the transition towards sustainable Blue Food systems?”**, while exploring the tools that can be used to attain this objective.

5.1.1 The role of consumer attitude.

Alessandro Galli, Senior scientist from the [Global Footprint network](#), presented his study **“Reducing Mediterranean Seafood Footprints:**

The role of consumer attitudes”¹⁴. The study starts from the observation that food systems are the main drivers of human pressure on ecosystems in the Mediterranean region. Based on this, fish and seafood consumption plays an important role in carbon emissions and impacts on ecosystems. Therefore, **diversification of seafood preferences** could reduce the pressure on the environment, the question being how we can influence consumer behaviour so that they can, by their consumption habits, actually reduce the impacts of seafood production. The main objectives of the study were to identify the **externalities** of the dietary habits of consumers in three Mediterranean countries - **Italy, Croatia** and **Turkey** - and to assess which consumers in one of these countries would be more willing to change their dietary choices. The study ultimately aims to understand what are the consumers’ perceptions of sustainability, and what prevents them from eating differently.

Results of the study “Reducing Mediterranean Seafood Footprints: The role of consumer attitudes”.

Source: Extract from the slides presented by Alessandro Galli.

¹⁴ Selen Altiok, Adeline Murthy, Katsunori Iha, Alessandro Galli, “Reducing Mediterranean Seafood Footprints: The role of consumer attitudes”, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 214, 2021, 105915, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105915>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0964569121003987>)

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First of all, results show that in all three countries, most people consume **1 to 2 servings per week**, with Italian consumers eating more diverse types of food. The biggest barriers to purchasing unfamiliar seafood are price, unknown flavors and cooking methods. The first criteria taken into account by consumers in all three countries is the **freshness of products**. For Croatian and Turkish

consumers, price is the second main driver, while health and nutritional benefits is the second driver in Italy. Then, the willingness to change consumer attitudes, measured in relation with the consumers' interest in trying new products and the habit of looking for alternatives, is high in Italy and Turkey, but lower in Croatia where there is a lack of interest in trying new products.

Results of the study "Reducing Mediterranean Seafood Footprints: The role of consumer attitudes".

Source: Extract from the slides presented by Alessandro Galli.

Finally, on the perception of sustainability of **Small Scale Fisheries (SSF)**, the study has found that the highest shares of respondents perceive SSF as more sustainable than Large Scale Fisheries (LSF) within the consumers that have the lowest knowledge of SSF. This confirms

the idea that, in order to increase the market penetration rate of SSF, strategies should include an improved communication about the role and sustainability of SSF.

5.1.2 European innovation in the food sector

Begoña Perez, Director of EIT Food South, presented EIT Food, an EU-funded innovation community dedicated to Education, Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Public engagement in the food sector. One of the innovation areas of EIT Food is **sustainable aquaculture**. As seafood

consumption increases, sustainable aquaculture must keep up with demand while continuing to provide many other economic, social and environmental benefits. Despite the numerous challenges, sustainable aquaculture has many advantages that we must take into

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account, including environmental benefits (low carbon footprint, ecosystem conservation and restoration...) and economic and social benefits (food security, seafood trade deficit, economic growth...). However, to benefit from these advantages, there are challenges to be tackled.

EIT Food has identified **4 key challenges** for their innovation community:

- Optimisation of production systems and supply chains
- New emerging sustainable production systems and aquaculture species
- Sustainable and healthy ecosystems
- Product safety and quality, consumer awareness and trust

To achieve these goals, EIT Food is launching a new **call for sustainable aquaculture** at the beginning of november. On challenge number 4, more specifically, the objective is to work on public perception issues, to remedy the lack of tools to enhance the high protein values of seafood, and to determine fraud and origin of products coming from outside of the EU.

5.1.3 The role of consumers, markets and lifestyle

All in all, the figure below underlines the idea that a change in consumer's attitude towards sustainable blue food is possible when gaining new information about them. For instance, during the debate a participant raised the question of what is characterized by **"fresh" fish**, and brought attention to the problem of defrozen fish, which is sold in supermarkets without indicating that it was defrozen, and in which conditions. However, as Alessandro Galli's study suggests, consumers will prefer it to the frozen fish because it seems fresh. Besides, speakers mentioned the importance of effectiveness in ecolabels as well as in the ecodesign of fish products. Lastly, as far as industrial eco-innovation is concerned, participants of the discussion claimed that innovation is incipient. Consequently, there are still many challenges to address, especially in terms of production systems or species diversification.

Key concepts presented in the discussion on the role of consumers, markets and lifestyle

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5.2. GOVERNANCE AND POLICIES

The second discussion, on the topic of Governance and Policies, was facilitated by **Lydia Chaparro**, marine policy officer at Fundació ENT. She initiated this session stressing the importance of changing the way seafood is harvested, consumed and regulated in order to promote a resilient food system and reduce carbon emissions. Bringing back the idea that achieving sustainability is challenging on a global scale, Chaparro emphasised that she prefers to stick to a more realistic terminology, by using adjectives such as less production or less emissions, instead of 'sustainable' when describing the blue food industry. Besides, she notes that, according to the FAO, the Mediterranean is the most **overexploited sea** in the world. Hence, it is crucial to work towards more resilient marine ecosystems which offer us more food and more protein to address the social challenges of the Mediterranean region. Some key concepts align particularly well with today's

definition of governance, including **marine spatial planning, stakeholder engagement and participatory processes** to involve all actors (government, research institutes, civil society, non-governmental organizations, markets) in the decision-making process of marine policies.

5.2.1 European Marine Policies

Tobias Troll introduced the **European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**. It is the overarching EU environmental regulatory framework with the ambition to reach good environmental status of the European seas. This framework interacts with the other policies in force like the European Commission's Marine Spatial Planning tool, its Sustainable Blue Economy strategy, and the Common Fisheries Policy. The MSFD is composed of 11 qualitative indicators which assist in reaching the goal, i.e., the good environmental status.

11 qualitative indicators of the MSFD.

Source: Extract from the slides presented by Tobias Troll (Seas At Risk)

The good environmental status was set to be achieved in 2020. However, its high ambition, weak implementation and the lack of policy coherence with other policies, like fisheries

policies, prevented it from reaching success. The directive is currently under review, which included a public consultation (closed since 21 October 2021)¹⁵.

¹⁵ Find more detail [here](#).

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5.2.1 Sustainable Consumption and Production

Magali Outters, Team Leader Policy Area at the [Sustainable Consumption and Production Regional Activity Center](#) located in Barcelona, and member of the [SwitchMed initiative](#), introduced her presentation stressing the interesting perspectives offered by Blue Food. These include increasing the supply of quality proteins, reducing the ecological footprint of food systems, offering jobs for local communities and promoting the growth of this sector. However, whenever growth is involved, environmental, health and social aspects are often forgotten, and we only start to act once the damage is done. To transform the Blue Food sector, growing rapidly in the Mediterranean region, it is necessary to use lessons learned in other sectors, the main message being that there is not one single recipe and that we need a mix of actions between taxes and subsidies, regulatory measures and consumer sensibilization. It is also important to ensure the effective implementation of policies, especially in the Southern coast of the Mediterranean where there is often a lack of actual execution. In terms of more precise actions, the priority would be to eliminate all subsidies to harmful activities like unsustainable fishing. It is also necessary to work on economic incentives, that need to include environmental requirements, and on innovation, as many more things are still to be developed in the Blue Food sector.

Following this, Magali Outters linked these issues with other challenges in the Mediterranean region, **including plastic pollution and chemical products**. Concerning the first one, she reminded that the Mediterranean Sea has the highest concentration of plastic waste, which is a problem in itself, but that also affects fishing. This concentration of plastic also causes a problem of chemical pollution, as they contain toxic chemicals such as endocrine disruptors which are then found in sea products sold to consumers. However, chemical pollution also has to do with the way aquaculture is organised

today. The use of antibiotics in aquaculture for example creates chemical pollution, which in turn hurts human and ocean health. Lastly, Magali Outters presented the Regional Activity Center's activities, starting with its proposals for regional measures to develop green and circular businesses, which includes companies with a focus on Blue economy sectors. A Decision including the measures should be adopted by the Barcelona Convention at COP22 at the end of this year. The SwitchMed initiative is also starting activities to support entrepreneurship in Blue economy sectors in South Mediterranean countries.

5.2.2 Circular economy in fisheries and aquaculture

Carolina Pérez, [MedCities'](#) Project officer, presented the [BLUEfasma](#) project, which seeks to promote Circular Economy through fisheries and aquaculture. The project works with small and medium enterprises in the value chain of this sector, giving them tools to implement circularity in the value chain and helping them to boost innovation. The aim is to train and sensitize both the seller and the consumer. These objectives are achieved with the creation of living labs, in partnership with the [ENT Foundation](#). 11 of these participatory experiences have been organized in 9 different countries with different themes such as energy and transport, waste prevention, fish revaluation, financing.

Now, members of the project, together with the other stakeholders, are working on **policy recommendations** to encourage this transformation. There is a big area for improvement to bridge the gap between research advances and the economic sector (SMEs), in order for innovations to be effectively used by the Blue food production sector. She also stressed that legislative frameworks must adapt to allow for and incentivise innovation, making come together the Blue Economy and the **Circular Economy** policy agendas for the fisheries and aquaculture sector value chain.

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There is also a need for the sector to boost further awareness and to create incentives and finance mechanisms (including support to improve sustainability of infrastructure, equipment and materials). Another recommendation derived from **BLUEfasma's** preliminary findings is to develop Circular Economy training schemes and to foster awareness addressing the whole value chain, including consumers. Lastly, Carolina Pérez expressed the need to bolster this transformation in the whole basin. In sum, the sector needs technical, legal, economic and financial support to embrace the circular economy as a driver for transformation.

5.2.3 The Mediterranean diet and Regional observatory

Juliette Olivier, Policy and Project Officer at the Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR) in the Intermediterranean Commission, presented the Conference, a network of approximately 150 regions created in 1973, and working to structure a more balanced development of European territory. To achieve this objective, it works both as a lobby and a think tank, and is organized in 6 geographical commissions, including the Intermediterranean Commission, aimed at stimulating the **Blue economy, sustainability and cohesion**.

CPMR Mediterranean network

Source: Extract from the slides presented by Juliette Olivier (CPMR)

The Commission has launched the **AgriMed** taskforce on sustainable agriculture and food sovereignty, after the publication of the ARLEM report, which highlights the challenges of Mediterranean agriculture. Amongst the different challenges it identified, Juliette Olivier particularly stressed the ones regarding

governance deficit and overexploitation and waste of food resources. Food systems are rarely in the priorities of policy-makers, the environmental impact of food production is not sufficiently taken into account and short-term profitability often prevails. Once these challenges were identified, the report wrote

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recommendations, which include revalorizing the Mediterranean diet as well as supporting food security. Regarding the first recommendation, Juliette Olivier recalled that the Mediterranean diet was recognized as intangible heritage by UNESCO in 2010. As a diet rich in nutrients and strongly based on fish consumption, it opens many perspectives for the improvement of **Blue food systems**.

To implement these recommendations, the Agrimed TaskForce will focus on two main operational propositions. The first one consists of building a **“Euro-Mediterranean Observatory of Agricultural Markets, Resilient Agri-Environmental Practices and Sustainable Food Systems”**, dedicated to sharing good practices between actors at the local and regional scales. The second one would be to structure a “Mediterranean Products” or **“Mediterranean Diet” label**: capitalizing on already existing labels, to guarantee Mediterranean products are healthy and nutritious, and to better inform consumers. Lastly, Juliette Olivier insisted on the importance of linking agriculture and fisheries issues in terms of governance as there are many lessons to be shared, while associating the different levels of governance to promote the replication of initiatives between regions.

5.2.4 The UNEP/MAP - Barcelona Convention system and the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development.

Julien Le Tellier, Programme Management Officer in charge of Socio-Economic Affairs at the UN Environment Programme/Mediterranean Action Plan - Barcelona Convention Secretariat, presented the organization, dedicated to translating international commitments and the environment policy agenda at the Mediterranean level to fulfill the vision of a healthy Mediterranean Sea and Coast that underpin sustainable development in the region. This is achieved also by cooperating with the regional fisheries management organization, i.e. FAO-GFCM.

Julien Le Tellier announced that the COP22 of the **Barcelona Convention** will be held in Antalya, Turkey, from 7-10 December 2021. The agenda of COP22 will include the adoption of the UNEP/MAP medium-term strategy 2022-2027, with a thematic program on the **sustainable blue economy**, “Towards the sustainable use of coastal and marine resources including circular and blue economy”.

Julien Le Tellier mentioned the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development 2016-2025 (MSSD), which provides an integrative policy framework for all stakeholders and partners to translate the global 2030 Agenda and the SDGs at regional, sub-regional, national and local levels. The MSSD aims at investing in the environment to achieve sustainable social and economic development, with a cross-cutting objective focusing on natural resource management and food security.

This strategy should be revised in the coming years, taking into consideration the issues raised in the BEF 2021 discussions. Future review and developments of the strategy will be achieved in an inclusive process, for which UNEP/MAP would rely on the support of key stakeholders such as those present at the BEF 2021. Building on issues discussed among other speakers, population growth is an important driver because it translates into an increased demand for protein, and therefore more pressure on food systems. In the Mediterranean region, **80% of fisheries are artisanal (small-scale fisheries)**, which implies that this activity has direct social and economic impacts for local communities. If we hope to benefit from more generous fish stocks, which have experienced unprecedented collapse, the most problematic one in the world, reasoned practices respectful of marine conservation are required. Considering the increasing demand for seafood, as shown in this article, aquaculture is considered as essential by many. However, one must not forget that it causes real damage to the environment, and therefore to communities, meaning that this activity must be supervised

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and regulated, including in the framework of regional cooperation and partnerships. This requires observation, harmonized monitoring, national case studies in the major aquaculture producing countries, and special focus on local territories to monitor the environmental footprint of aquaculture farms.

Julien Le Tellier referred to the report on the **State of the Environment and Development in the Mediterranean**, which has been prepared by Plan Bleu, a UNEP/MAP Regional Activity Centre. This important regional assessment report provides an interesting synthesis on the blue economy sectors, although trends are moving very fast, making monitoring and observation systems necessary to ensure that this sector continues to prosper in harmony with nature.

5.2.5. The role of governance and policies

All in all, the figure below provides a grasp of concepts presented during the dialogue. In relation to the key actors involved in the governance of Blue Food Systems in the Mediterranean, the coalitions of development

actors were featured such as Seas at Risk, as well as the partnerships with small and medium sized enterprises and public institutions. Moreover, transformational leaders and change agents were introduced in the discussion too.

On another note, some of the current ocean governance trends which were highlighted correspond with the participatory type of governance and the creation of synergies. Special emphasis was put on the search for synergies within the EU/Mediterranean regulatory framework, for instance the interrelation of MSP strategies with Blue Economy programs. Lastly, speakers stressed the need for more policy coherence, faster impact assessment processes with a unified set of criteria and indicators, stronger coaction with industries and more legal support to bolster sustainability in the Blue Economy sector.

Key concepts presented in the discussion on governance and policies

Source: [eco-union](https://www.eco-union.eu)

6 PERSPECTIVES FOR BLUE FOOD IN THE MEDITERRANEAN REGION

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As pointed out by **Isidro González Alfonso**, General Secretary of the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM); 7% of the world's population lives in the Mediterranean region, but only 3% of the world's water is located there. Besides, it is the most affected region by climate change after the Arctic (as temperatures rise up at a rate which is 20% faster than the world's average). Hence, dialogue is no longer an option, it is a must. As the development of the Mediterranean region strongly depends on the coordinated efforts of all countries. The Mediterranean sea occupies only 1% of the Earth's surface, notwithstanding that about one-third of the international shipping industry moves about its coasts.

There are studies supporting that in 2050 there will be **more plastic than fish** in the ocean. On top of that, fish size would be affected with a decrease between 50 and 80%. In economic terms the ocean economy is currently the seventh global economy. Therefore, efforts should be placed on building synergies amongst the shipping and the food industry. It is clear that food production and consumption need to reduce their impacts on the ocean-climate, though there is still a long way to go to revert this trend. However, it is crucial to foster events and projects that promote a rich exchange of ideas in order to build new knowledge, as they facilitate the way to jointly achieve desired efforts for a more sustainable blue food system.

7 CONCLUSION: THE WAY TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE MEDITERRANEAN BLUE FOOD

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In conclusion, the BEF 2021 has put emphasis on the fact that flourishing ideas and innovation in the sector of **Blue Food** are all **opportunities** to make Blue Food more sustainable. Adapting general principles used in other sectors, such as **Circular Economy**, seems like a particularly interesting way to transform the sector to reach a positive environmental impact. Alternatively, thinking in terms of scale brings attention to the fact that scaling down the production, instead of concentrating activities, has many benefits in terms of environmental consequences.

Despite this, there are also **challenges** to be addressed. **Accelerating the Blue Food transition** calls for **systemic changes**. It requires a greater understanding of consumers' attitude towards alternative food, and raising awareness of the need to diversify our Blue Food diets, not only among the consumers but also among industries. Moreover, sound governance is necessary to bolster such a **sustainable transformation across the Mediterranean basin**. It requires to design better integrated policies, to build synergies to guarantee policy coherence, to offer stronger legal support and to promote participatory modes of governance in the Mediterranean basin including market, state and civil society actors. More generally, updating the terminology and avoiding terms such as sustainability, that have lost their meanings over time, could make messages more impactful.

Altogether, it is clear there are still obstacles to overcome. Nevertheless, the participants have gathered valuable and inspiring insights to push forward a more sustainable Blue Food System for the sake of the Mediterranean region's future. Fortunately, we could expect the political momentum around Blue Food to be maintained, considering that the UN has declared 2022 the International Year of Artisanal Fisheries and Aquaculture and organizes the Ocean Conference in Portugal in June 2022.

8 ANNEX: AGENDA OF THE EVENT

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9h - 9h15: WELCOME

- **Jérémie Fosse**, President, eco-union
- **Pau Solanilla**, Commissioner, Barcelona City Hall
- **Michael Scoullos**, Chairman, MIO-ECSDE

9h15 - 10h: SETTING THE BLUE TABLE: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR A SUSTAINABLE BLUE FOOD ECO- SYSTEM IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

Relevant stakeholders and international experts will explore the challenges, opportunities, barriers and needs related to sustainable blue food ecosystem in the Mediterranean region, with a special focus on environmental impacts, governance issues, behavioral, management or market instruments.

- **Malin Jonell**, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Blue Food Assessment initiative
- **Housam Hamza**, Aquaculture Officer, General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM/FAO)
- **Sandro Dernini**, Coordinator, SFS-MED Platform Coordination Desk

* *Moderator: Tobias Troll, Marine Policy Director, Seas At Risk*

10h00 - 10h30: BLUE PITCHES FROM INNOVATIVE ACTORS OF THE MEDITERRANEAN BLUE FOOD ECOSYSTEM

- **Patricia Ricard**, president, Paul Ricard Oceanographic Institute: a private research institute applying Circular Economy principles and Nature-based solutions to aquaculture systems.
- **Yago Sierras**, Mediterranean Algae: Spanish startup (Alicante) dedicated to the cultivation of algae native to the Mediterranean Sea, in a sustainable way.
- **Marika Azoff**, The Good Food Institute, a global nonprofit organization promoting a sustainable, secure, and just food system with alternative proteins like plant-based and cultivated seafood.

8 ANNEX: AGENDA OF THE EVENT

10h30-11h50: COOKING THE BLUE RECIPE: INTERACTIVE DISCUSSIONS ON SUSTAINABLE BLUE FOOD TRANSITION(S)

This session will draft a collective diagnosis on key environmental, social and economic issues related to Sustainable Blue Food in the Mediterranean, based on the following questions: What are the key issues to be addressed in the current Mediterranean food system? What are the key actors and their role? Which policies, strategies and market instruments can contribute to a more sustainable blue food system?

10h30-11h10: CONSUMERS, MARKETS AND LIFESTYLE

How can Consumers behaviors, lifestyle changes, market tools and industrial eco-innovations participate in the transition towards more sustainable blue food systems in the Mediterranean? Facilitated by Laia Segura (eco-union), with introductory notes from:

- **Alessandro Galli**, Senior scientist, Global Footprint Network: Reducing Mediterranean Seafood Footprints: The role of consumer attitudes.
- **Begoña Perez Villarreal**, Director EIT Food South, European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) Food: Public research driving innovation in aquaculture and food sector in Europe

11h10-11h50: GOVERNANCE AND POLICIES

What regulations and public policies can ensure a sustainable deployment of blue food systems in the Mediterranean? Facilitated by Lydia Chaparro (ENT Foundation), with introductory notes from:

- **Tobias Troll**, Marine Policy Director, Seas At Risk: EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive
- **Magali Outters**, Policy Leader, SwitchMed: Sustainable Consumption and Production
- **Carolina Perez**, MedCities & Barcelona Metropolitan Area: Blue Fasma project
- **Juliette Olivier**, Policy and Project Officer, CPRM – Intermediterranean Commission

11h50 - 12h SAILING THE BLUE: ROADMAP TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE MEDITERRANEAN BLUE FOOD

This closing debate will discuss ideas and proposals on how to contribute to a multi-stakeholders Blue food initiative in the Mediterranean involving key public and private actors at local, national and regional level.

- **Isidro González Afonso**, Deputy Secretary General, Water & Environment, Union for the Mediterranean
- **Jérémie Fosse**, president, eco-union

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